

Ionic Interaction Coefficients : Activity Calculations in Mixed Electrolyte Solutions in Ion Exchange Studies

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The ionic interaction coefficients of a number of electrolytes of different valence types have been calculated by the use of the Bronsted-Scatchard-Guggenheim equation, utilising the activity coefficient values of the solutions of pure electrolytes. Herefrom have been calculated the net ionic interaction coefficients for mixtures of two electrolytes in solution, e.g. those occurring in the expressions for the thermodynamic equilibrium constant in ion-exchange studies. The total mixture molarity in these (intended constant-ionic-strength) exchange studies having had perforce to be varied within appropriate (albeit smallest possible) ranges for various reasons, especially in the case of heterovalent ion exchange, the variation of the net interaction coefficients over the mixture molarity ranges involved, is of interest to consider. This has been shown graphically, in the case of sixteen cation and anion exchange systems ($\mu \sim 0.1$) investigated.

IN ion exchange reactions between ions fixed on solid exchanger matrix with those in the equilibrium electrolyte solution, the evaluation of the thermodynamic equilibrium constant requires a knowledge of the activity coefficient values of the electrolytes in the mixed solution^{1,2}. For the accurate estimation of these the following methods have been used :

(i) The first is the application of Harned's rule³ which predicts that the logarithm of the activity coefficient of one electrolyte AX in a mixture is proportional to the molality of the other electrolyte AY , i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \log \gamma_{AX} &= \log \gamma_{AX}^{\circ} - \alpha_{AX} m_{AY} \\ \log \gamma_{AY} &= \log \gamma_{AY}^{\circ} - \alpha_{AY} m_{AX} \end{aligned} \quad \dots (1)$$

γ_{AX}° and γ_{AY}° being respectively the activity coefficient of pure AX and AY in solutions of ionic strength equal to that of the mixture, and α is a constant (a function of the total mixture molality, m)³. These α coefficients can be determined by isopiestic⁴ or potentiometric methods^{3,5}. Sengupta *et al*⁶, have calculated, by a slight extrapolation of such α -values⁴, the activity coefficient values of $CaCl_2$ and $MgCl_2$ in their mutual mixtures, for use in Ca^{++} - Mg^{++} exchange systems.

(ii) The α -coefficients can also be calculated by use of the Brönsted⁷, Scatchard⁸ and Guggenheim's⁹ principle of specific ionic interactions :

$$\log \gamma_i = Z_i^2 \log \gamma^{St} + \sum_j B_{ij} m_j \quad \dots (2)$$

$\log \gamma^{St}$ being the Debye-Hückel expression for ionic activity coefficient and B_{ij} a coefficient characteristic

of the interaction between i and j type of ions. By use of such equations for the individual ions, the expression for the mean activity coefficient of one electrolyte ($AZ_2 XZ_1$) in presence of another ($AZ_3 YZ_1$) in a mixture, can easily be written down :

$$\begin{aligned} \log \gamma_{A_{z(2)}X_{z(1)}} &= |Z_1| |Z_2| \log \gamma^{St} + B_{A_{z(2)}X_{z(1)}} \\ &\times \left[\frac{2 \cdot Z_1 \cdot Z_2}{Z_1 + Z_2} m_{A_{z(2)}X_{z(1)}} + \frac{Z_1 Z_3}{Z_1 + Z_2} m_{A_{z(3)}Y_{z(1)}} \right] \\ &+ \frac{Z_1 Z_2}{Z_1 + Z_2} B_{A_{z(2)}Y_{z(1)}} m_{A_{z(3)}Y_{z(1)}} \quad \dots (3) \end{aligned}$$

Herefrom one also obtains the following expression for the activity coefficient of a pure electrolyte $AZ_2 XZ_1$:

$$\begin{aligned} \log \gamma_{A_{z(2)}X_{z(1)}}^{\circ} &= |Z_1| |Z_2| \log \gamma^{St} \\ &+ \frac{2 Z_1 Z_2}{Z_1 + Z_2} B_{A_{z(2)}X_{z(1)}} m_{A_{z(2)}X_{z(1)}} \quad \dots (4) \end{aligned}$$

$m_{A_{z(2)}X_{z(1)}}$ being the molality of the electrolyte in mixture. The above equation serves to determine the value of the specific interaction coefficient $B_{A_{z(2)}X_{z(1)}}$, which can then be used to calculate the activity coefficient of the electrolyte $AZ_2 XZ_1$ in mixed solution by equation (3). The B values thus calculated have been used by Boyd *et al.*¹ for evaluation of the solution phase activity coefficient ratio for the Zn^{++} - Na^+ exchange system, and similarly by others^{6,10} for some other exchange systems.

For electrolytes obeying Harned's rule, the α -coefficients of equation (1) may be shown to be related to the B coefficients^{5,9}; for example, for a mixture

of two electrolytes AZ_2XZ_1 and AZ_2YZ_1 , with a common cation A :

$$\alpha_{A_{z(2)}X_{z(1)}} = \frac{1}{2}\nu(B_{A_{z(2)}X_{z(1)}} - B_{A_{z(2)}Y_{z(1)}}) \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha_{A_{z(2)}Y_{z(1)}} = \frac{1}{2}\nu(B_{A_{z(2)}Y_{z(1)}} - B_{A_{z(2)}X_{z(1)}})$$

ν being the harmonic mean of the number of cations and anions in one molecule of the corresponding electrolyte. Using such equations, the simple ratio of the activity coefficients of two 1-1 electrolytes obeying Harned's rule can easily be shown to be given by an equation of the type² :

$$\log \frac{\gamma_{AX}}{\gamma_{AY}} = \log \frac{\gamma_{AX}^0}{\gamma_{AY}^0} - 0.4342(\beta_{AX} - \beta_{AY})m \quad \dots (6)$$

the β 's being related to the B 's :

$$B_{AX} = 0.4342(2\beta_{AX}). \quad \dots (7)$$

Tables of β values compiled by Guggenheim¹¹ for some 1-1 strong electrolytes for a constant mixture ionic strength of 0.1 m have been made use of by Boyd, Lindenbaum and Myers², and others^(10a), for evaluating the activity coefficient ratio of 1-1 electrolytes involved in exchange reactions of univalent halides.

In general, for ion exchange reactions involving different valence type ions, different types of ratio terms of the activity coefficients of the two electrolytes, depending upon their respective valence types, appear in the expression for the mass action constant. Such ratio terms can however be determined by the application of the equations (3) and (4) directly. For example, for a mixture of two 1-1 electrolytes⁶ :

$$\log \frac{\gamma_{\pm AX}^2}{\gamma_{\pm AY}^2} = Bm \quad \dots (8)$$

where

$$B = B_{AX} - B_{AY}. \quad \dots (9)$$

Equations such as the above been used by Sengupta *et al*⁶ in the calculation of the equilibrium constant of $Ag^+ - H^+$ exchange reaction*. Similarly, for mixtures of (i) a 1-1 and a 1-2 (or a 1-1 and a 2-1),

* The above equations can be shown to be equivalent to the earlier formulated equation (6) if the pure electrolyte activity coefficients $\log \gamma_{AX}^0$ and $\log \gamma_{AY}^0$ are assumed to be given by the B.S.G. expressions,

$$0.4342 \left[\frac{-\alpha\sqrt{I}}{1+1.5\sqrt{I}} + 2\beta_{AX}.m \right]$$

and

$$0.4342 \left[\frac{-\alpha\sqrt{I}}{1+1.5\sqrt{I}} + 2\beta_{AY}.m \right]$$

respectively; the β 's are related to B 's as in equation (7);

$\frac{-\alpha\sqrt{I}}{1+1.5\sqrt{I}}$ is the Debye-Hückel term; and m is the total molality of the mixed solution.

(ii) two 2-1, (iii) a 2-1 and a 3-1, (iv) a 2-1 and a 4-1, and (v) a 3-1 and a 4-1 electrolytes, the expressions for the corresponding ratio terms of the activity coefficients of the two electrolytes entering into the expressions for the corresponding exchange reaction equilibrium constant, in terms of the B coefficients of the constituent electrolytes, have been given elsewhere^{6,12}.

Now since the interaction coefficients (B) of the individual electrolytes vary with concentration, therefore the variation of the net interaction coefficients with the total mixture molarity becomes of some interest to consider; it is the purpose of the present paper to investigate this aspect in reference to our ion exchange studies reported recently^{6,12}.

Calculations of B Coefficients for Ion Exchange Systems :

The cation and anion exchange equilibria studies^{6,13} reported earlier using synthetic organic ion exchangers Amberlite IR 120 and Amberlite IRA 400 respectively, are : $Ag^+ - H^+$, $Cu^{++} - H^+$, $Ag^+ - Cu^{++}$, $H^+ - Ca^{++}$, $H^+ - Mg^{++}$, $H^+ - Ba^{++}$, $Ba^{++} - Mg^{++}$, $Ba^{++} - La^{+++}$, $Ba^{++} - Th^{++++}$, $La^{+++} - Th^{++++}$, $CrO_4^{--} - Cl^-$, $CrO_4^{--} - I^-$, $SO_4^{--} - Cl^-$, $SO_4^{--} - I^-$, $H_2PO_4^{--} - Cl^-$, $H_2PO_4^{--} - SO_4^{--}$, $SO_4^{--} - CrO_4^{--}$. The equilibria were studied by the batch technique, starting mostly from both of the two pure resinate forms involved. A mixture ionic strength approximately equal to 0.1 was sought to be maintained; however, this has not always been possible, because in unsymmetrical exchanges it is the net normality, and not the ionic strength of the equilibrium solution, which remains constant, so that depending upon the extent of the unsymmetrical exchange undergone, different resultant equilibrium-solution ionic strengths are arrived at. Further, when the entering ion was not the preferred ion, higher concentrations of it in the aqueous phase had perforce to be used sometimes to achieve any significant extent of loading of the resin.

The solution phase activity coefficients of the component electrolytes in the mixtures were calculated by the Bronsted, Scatchard and Guggenheim method discussed above*. For this, the B -coefficients of the individual electrolytes were calculated by making use of the activity coefficient values of the pure electrolytes at the same molality as that of the mixture, according to the equation (4). Herefrom was calculated the value of the net interaction coefficient ' B ' for any mixture of two electrolytes partaking in an exchange reaction; these were then used to calculate the corrected activity coefficient ratio.

Now, in as much as the total mixture molarity in the case of unsymmetrical exchanges could not be maintained constant for reasons mentioned earlier, as also because the B coefficients are known to vary with concentration, therefore in order for the B

* Except in the case of $Cl^- - I^-$ and $Ca^{++} - Mg^{++}$ mixtures, for which methods of calculation described above were used.

values evaluated from equation (4) for pure electrolytes to be valid also for the mixtures (equation 3), it was necessary that the total molarities in these two cases be as nearly identical to one another as possible. The magnitude of the B coefficient for each electrolyte was therefore properly determined by evaluating it separately over a number of different concentration ranges spanning the actual range of variation of the concentration of all equilibrium solutions, in case of any particular exchange†. For doing this, the entire range of variation of all equilibrium solution molarities was first divided up into a number of sets of almost-identical-total-molarity-value mixtures; the B values of the two electrolytes in the mixture corresponding to each such almost constant total molarity was then evaluated as described; herefrom were calculated the different net B values for any mixture.

The variation of the net interaction coefficient, B , with total mixture molarity for a number of electrolyte mixtures enumerated earlier has been shown in the following figure††. The range of variation of the

† In the study of Zn^{++} - Na^+ exchange on Dowex-50W, Boyd, Vaslow and Lindenbaum have used B_{NaNO_3} and $B_{Zn(NO_3)_2}$ values calculated only for 0.1M pure $NaNO_3$ and $Zn(NO_3)_2$ solutions.

†† Except for the Ba^{++} - La^{+++} , Ba^{++} - Th^{++++} and La^{+++} - Th^{++++} systems, the B values for which have not been shown, The sign of the calculated B 's as shown in the figure (some +ve and others -ve) results from the fact that the exchange equilibrium was written in each case in such a manner as to render the equilibrium constant positive; with a consistently reversed calculation of the different K_x values, the B values shown negative here would become positive, and vice-versa.

total mixture molarity corresponds roughly to the neighbourhood of the mixture-ion-strength-range of interest to us (namely, ~ 0.1).

Results and Discussion

In general, the variation of the net B values with the total mixture molarity for the different binary electrolytes mixtures considered shows an initial portion where B either

- (I) increases (i) very rapidly, or (ii) rather more moderately, or,
 - (II) decreases slowly,
- followed in each case by a very gradually decreasing or almost constant stretch.

I. (i) The initial steep rise portion, over small total molarity values, has been observed particularly in the case of mixtures containing multivalent cations (here, for the molarity range studied, the subsequent stage of slow decrease or constancy of B was not reached): (a) For La^{+++} - Ba^{++} mixtures, B increases sharply from -1.355 to -0.796 as the total molarity of the mixture increases from 0.067 to 0.112, (b) For Ba^{++} - Th^{++++} mixtures, B increases rapidly from -2.407 to -1.171 for an increase in the total molarity from about 0.1082 to 0.171, (c) For Th^{++++} - La^{+++} mixtures only a very small range of variation of total mixture molarity was studied (0.05 to 0.065); over this range again B increases very sharply from -5.91 to -4.42 , (d) For Ag^+ - Cu^{++} mixtures also a sharp rise of B with total mixture molarity has been observed; this is an isolated case in this category, comprising of a pair of relatively low valent electrolytes.

(ii) A somewhat more gradual but otherwise similar initial increase of B followed by a more or less constant stretch over a rather large range of total mixture molarities (approx. 0.03 to 0.3) has been observed for $Mg^{++}-H^+$, $Ca^{++}-H^+$, $Cu^{++}-H^+$, and $CrO_4^{--}-Cl^-$ mixtures; the $CrO_4^{--}-I^-$ mixture also shows an apparently similar starting trend; however the total molarity range considered here was smaller (approx. 0.04–0.1).

II. A very gradual initial decrease of B followed again by an almost constant stretch over a somewhat smaller range of total mixture molarities studied (approx. 0.04–0.2) has been observed for $Ba^{++}-Mg^{++}$, $SO_4^{--}-Cl^-$ and $SO_4^{--}-I^-$ mixtures; the H^+-Ba^{++} and $H_2PO_4^- - SO_4^{--}$ mixtures also show an apparently similar trend; however the molarity range considered was rather small.

The net B coefficients considered above are of significance only in case of equilibrium study of ion exchange type reactions, where the earlier mentioned ratio terms of the solution phase activity coefficients of the constituent electrolytes are involved. Generally, it may be more meaningful to consider the characteristics (e.g., the variation with the total mixture molarity) of the B coefficients of the individual electrolytes involved. Also, in such studies, as wide a range of variation of total mixture molarity

would be desirable as is feasible in any particular case. Such studies are under way, and will be reported elsewhere.¹³

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